

CERTIFICATE

◆◆◆ THIS CERTIFICATE IS PROUDLY PRESENTED TO ◆◆◆

O'ZBEKISTONDA TA'LIM-TARBIYA JARAYONIGA INNOVATSION
YONDASHUVLAR.MUAMMO VA YECHIMLAR MAVZUSIDA RESPUBLIKA
ILMIY ONLINE KONFERENSIYASIDA FAOL ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN

Isomov Ilhomjon

**ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF CREATION OF A FAVORABLE
FOREIGN INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN**

**NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN
TAQDIRLANADI**

2023-MAY

